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*Highlights (for review)

A novel index, the Radar Burn Ratio (RBR) was developed for fire severity estimation

Empirical and generalized models based on standardized RBR values were compared

RBR showed comparable trends over a wide range of fires

The RBR index most sensitive to fire severity was based on HV backscatter

Similar estimation accuracies were obtained for both empirical and generalized models

1 **Radar Burn Ratio for fire severity estimation at canopy level: an example for temperate forests**

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6 Abstract

7 Fires affect wide areas and their effects can be successfully estimated from a range of remote sensing sensors,
8 with synthetic aperture radars (SAR) being of particular interest due to their sensitivity to forest vertical
9 structure, global availability and independence of cloud cover or solar elevation. Previous studies have
10 demonstrated the sensitivity to fire effects of L-band SAR sensors using post-fire datasets and empirical
11 modeling. This study proposed an innovative method for estimating fire severity by combining pre- and post-fire
12 SAR datasets within a change detection framework to compute a novel index, the Radar Burn Ratio (RBR).
13 More importantly, a standardized RBR was developed and tested over seven temperate forest types located on
14 three continents with above ground biomass values ranging from 30 to over 500 t ha⁻¹. RBR standardization
15 allowed for common thresholds to be defined and subsequently used for estimating the Composite Burn Index
16 (CBI, a measure of fire impact) without the need for *a priori* information (i.e., *in situ* data) on local post-fire
17 conditions. The estimation accuracy of the standardized RBR was compared to locally-calibrated empirical
18 models based on field CBI data. The results showed similar estimation errors and a strong agreement with the
19 reference *in situ* data (i.e., Cohen's weighted kappa > 0.61). The RBR index most sensitive to fire severity was
20 based on the cross-polarized channel applied under dry environmental conditions. Under wet conditions the
21 estimation accuracy was considerably lower. The methods proposed in this study are particularly valuable for
22 rapid fire severity assessments at regional to global scales, requiring only that RBR thresholds be calibrated for a
23 range of environments and that CBI scores be related to fuel consumption for each forest type.

24 1. Introduction

25 Fire is a critical forest disturbance agent globally (Kasischke et al. 2013). Worldwide, about 350 million hectares
26 are affected by fire annually (Van Der Werf et al. 2006), exerting a potentially major influence on carbon release

27 from terrestrial ecosystems (Andreae and Merlet 2001; Simmonds et al. 2005). Recent estimates show that about
28 2.1 PgC are released every year due to biomass burning, out of which about 15% come from the burning of
29 forests alone (Van Der Werf et al. 2010). Because of its importance, numerous approaches have been developed
30 to estimate fire impact. The assessment of immediate fire effects is referred to as fire severity, while the
31 assessment of the ecological or environmental response is referred to as burn severity (French et al. 2008).
32 Depending on ecological and management objectives, fire severity is measured using different indicators (Cocke
33 et al. 2005). A review of the field methods used to quantify fire impact shows that only a narrow range of
34 indicators are usually used (Kasischke et al. 2008). Such indicators depend on objectives, with vegetation related
35 characteristics (e.g. tree mortality, crown and stem damage, scorch height) being evaluated when focusing on
36 fire impacts on forests (Keyser et al. 2006; Knapp and Keeley 2006; Odion and Hanson 2006) and surface
37 characteristics (mineral soil exposure, organic layer depth, litter cover, water repellency, soil temperature, and
38 moisture) being evaluated when focusing on post fire processes such as seedling germination and survival
39 (Greene et al. 2007; Kasischke and Johnstone 2005; Lewis et al. 2006).

40 To estimate landscape level fire severity in conjunction with remote sensing, systematic field based approaches
41 such as the composite burn index (CBI (Key and Benson 2006)) and several variants (de Santis and Chuvieco
42 2009; Dillon et al. 2011) were developed. CBI uses a multi-strata approach to severity, with different factors
43 (e.g., litter, duff and dead fuel consumption, soil and rock cover/color, colonizing vegetation, percentage of
44 green/black/brown foliage, tree mortality) being scored for different forest strata (substrate, shrubs, understory
45 and various overstory layers). The average vegetation conditions are visually examined and the degree of change
46 with respect to the presumed pre-fire status is recorded for each individual factor in values from zero (no change)
47 to three (100% change). The scored factors are averaged by strata. Strata values are subsequently used to
48 produce severity scores for the understory (based on substrate, low shrubs and tall shrubs strata), overstory
49 (based on one or more tree strata) and the entire plot (based on all strata). The CBI was developed for temperate
50 forests in the US as a standardized approach, and was intended to yield comparable metrics from region to
51 region. The US Forest Service routinely uses CBI to assess fire severity within national programs such as the
52 Monitoring Trends in Burn Severity (Eidenshink et al. 2007). However, for other forest types (e.g., boreal) or for
53 non-forested areas, the CBI might not optimally describe fire effects, since it does not take into account

54 parameters such as changes in substrate (i.e. organic layer depth) which is important when differentiating along
55 the range of moderate to high severity levels (Epting et al. 2005; Hoy et al. 2008; Murphy et al. 2008; Smith et
56 al. 2005).

57 Fire severity can be used to predict ecosystem responses such as soil erosion and post-fire vegetation recovery,
58 which in turn affect water cycles and biodiversity (Benyon and Lane 2013). Furthermore, fire severity is also
59 related to impacts in terms of loss of life, properties and suppression costs (Keeley et al. 2008). Therefore,
60 accurate information on fire severity spatial patterns is critical in fire management for evaluating post-fire effects
61 and designing mitigation activities. The poor spatial representation and the considerable effort to gather field
62 data make the use of remote sensing essential over large areas.

63 Fire severity estimation through remote sensing is possible with many different sensor types, but to varying
64 degrees of success. Fire severity can be tracked from optical sensors using vegetation indices such as the
65 normalized burn ratio (NBR) in conjunction with a range of fire severity measures (e.g., tree mortality, crown
66 damage, CBI scores etc.). However, reflectance based indexes often fail to produce accurate results, particularly
67 for intermediate severity levels where multiple effects combine (Tanase et al. 2011). In addition, reflectance-
68 based indices are sensitive to solar elevation and cloud cover, which further decrease their utility in boreal
69 environments (Verbyla et al. 2008). Recent studies showed that fire severity measured through CBI scores can
70 be estimated from active sensors such as radar or lidar (Tanase et al. 2014a; Tanase et al. 2010b; Tanase et al.
71 2010c; Wang and Glenn 2009). The empirical relationships observed in such studies were confirmed through
72 modelling approaches based on the radiative transfer theory (Kalogerou et al. 2014). Active sensors provide a
73 direct measure of vegetation structure, as they are sensitive to the quantity of scattering elements along the forest
74 canopy. Platforms using SAR sensors may be ideal for vegetation monitoring, as the signal is directly influenced
75 by vegetation structure and thus more sensitive to temporal changes in forest structure than optical data, and less
76 limited by spatial and temporal availability than lidar sensors. Previous studies have confirmed the utility of
77 post-fire radar-based metrics (i.e., backscatter intensities, interferometric and polarimetric decomposition
78 components) for fire severity estimation, particularly when using L-band wavelength (Tanase et al. 2010a;
79 Tanase et al. 2014b; Tanase et al. 2010b; Tanase et al. 2010c). L-band radar scattering from forests includes

80 components from the crown volume (mainly branches), direct backscatter from tree stems, dihedral scattering
81 from stems/branches and ground, and direct and attenuated (by the canopy) backscatter from the ground (Le
82 Toan et al. 1992). Over unburned forests, L-band cross-polarized (HV polarization) waves are dominated by
83 volumetric scattering from branches within the canopy layer while co-polarized (HH polarization) waves are
84 dominated by a combination of crown and dihedral scattering depending on forest structure (Burgin et al. 2011).
85 Additionally, cross-polarized backscatter is more responsive to changes in stem density and tree height, while
86 co-polarized backscatter is highly sensitive to increasing soil moisture (Burgin et al. 2011). For the particular
87 case of a burned forest, decreasing volume and dihedral scattering were observed with increasing fire severity
88 due to the reduction of scattering elements available within the forest canopy (Tanase et al. 2014b).

89 To date, only methods based on post-fire datasets have been used to estimate fire severity from SAR sensors
90 (Tanase et al. 2010a; Tanase et al. 2014b; Tanase et al. 2010b; Tanase et al. 2010c). Such studies demonstrated
91 strong relationships between SAR metrics and fire severity, as well as high estimation accuracies. Previous
92 studies also demonstrated that rainfall significantly affected the radar signal from burned areas, with increased
93 backscatter being attributed to decreased attenuation, strong stem-ground interactions, and changes in soil
94 moisture (Bourgeau-Chavez et al. 1994; Kasischke et al. 1994; Kasischke et al. 2011). Therefore, preference was
95 given to post-fire SAR datasets acquired under dry conditions when estimating fire severity, since wetter
96 conditions usually resulted in decreased sensitivity to fire severity (Tanase et al. 2010a). Another major factor
97 which could limit the applicability of SAR data for fire severity retrieval was topography. Uncorrected or
98 unaccounted for topographic effects considerably decreased fire severity estimation accuracy at all wavelengths
99 (Tanase et al. 2010a). Alternatively, a change detection approach based on the relative variations between pre-
100 and post- fire datasets has been used for remote sensing data acquired by optical sensors (Miller and Thode
101 2007). By using pre- and post-fire datasets, the effect of topography is cancelled out – a major advantage
102 compared to single date approaches where such effects have to be accounted for. To our knowledge, such change
103 detection approaches have not been used to derive fire severity estimates using SAR datasets. Previous studies
104 have also demonstrated that fire severity could be estimated from SAR-based metrics through empirical models
105 calibrated for local fire conditions using ancillary data (Tanase et al. 2010a; Tanase et al. 2014b; Tanase et al.
106 2010b; Tanase et al. 2010c). However, estimating fire severity without *a priori* information from field data is

107 important when assessing combustion completeness and the associated carbon emissions over wide and/or
108 remote areas, as well as for land management activities related to fire impact mitigation and the assessment of
109 residual carbon sink capacity, habitat loss, biodiversity, and water cycles. Mapping fire severity without field
110 data has been achieved by calibrating thresholds for optical-derived change indices, a straightforward image
111 classification technique (Key and Benson 2006; Miller and Thode 2007). Such an approach has not been applied
112 to SAR datasets. Therefore, the objectives of this study were to: i) develop a change detection framework, i.e.,
113 the Radar Burn Ratio (RBR), for fire severity estimation from SAR datasets; ii) test the accuracy of RBR indices
114 over a range of fire regimes using field datasets; iii) calibrate thresholds for standardized RBR indices to be
115 used for rapid fire severity assessment without the need of *a priori* field information; and iv) compare the
116 accuracy of the standardized RBR indices against empirical models derived using field estimates of severity.

117 2. Study areas

118 Nine fires were selected based on the availability of field estimates of fire severity and L-band datasets from the
119 Advanced Land Observing Satellite (ALOS) Phased Array type L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (PALSAR). L-
120 band wavelength was selected since previous studies showed its much higher sensitivity to fire severity when
121 compared to X- and C-band wavelengths (Tanase et al. 2010a). The fires were located in Australia, the United
122 States of America and Spain, and represented variable forest conditions as detailed in the following sections
123 (Fig. 1). In Australia, the largest contiguous area affected by fires during Black Saturday (February-March 2009)
124 -- the Kinglake Fire Complex -- was selected. Since the area affected by fire encompassed three forest types with
125 potentially different responses to fire, they were analyzed as three separate fires. In the US, three fires located in
126 California (Iron Complex), Oregon (Rooster Rock) and Washington (Columbia River Road) states were selected,
127 while in Spain further three fires were available for the analysis (Aliaga, Los Olmos, and Zuera). All fires burnt
128 between 2008 and 2009 except for Rooster Rock, which burnt in 2010.

129 2.1 Australia

130 The first study area was located in the Kinglake-Yarra Ranges National Parks, Victoria, Australia. The area is
131 dominated by mixed eucalypt forests. According to the Department of Environment and Primary Industries
132 (DEPI), Victoria, these forests are categorized within three main types: i) wet forest dominated by *Eucalyptus*

133 *regnans*, ii) damp forests dominated by mixed eucalypt species such as *E. obliqua* and *E. radiata* and, iii) forby
134 forests dominated by *E. obliqua*, *E. radiata* and *E. cypellocarpa* (Cheal 2010). Wet forests are characterized by
135 average ground biomass values in excess of 500 t ha⁻¹, with trees reaching heights up to 54 m (Fedrigo et al.
136 2014). The average tree height is 20 m and the average diameter at breast (DBH) is 40 cm (Table 1). Damp
137 forests are characterized by lower average biomass levels, 400 t ha⁻¹ and shorter trees, heights up to 32 m (C.
138 Aponte personal communication). The average tree height and DBH in damp forests are considerably smaller
139 when compared to wet forests, i.e., 17 m and 30 cm respectively. Forby forests are characterized by average
140 above ground biomass levels around 280 t ha⁻¹ and tree heights up to 32 m. The average tree height is 20 m and
141 the average diameter at breast height is 35 cm (C. Aponte personal communication).

142 Wildfire regimes in southeast Australia have been characterized by occasional (approximately 20 – 100 years)
143 high intensity fires (Murphy et al. 2013). Depending on survival strategy, eucalypt forests are grouped in
144 obligate seeders and resprouters, with both groups often being encountered within the same forest landscape
145 (Gill 1997). The seeders group is dominated by species that are most likely killed by high intensity fires (e.g. *E.*
146 *regnans*, *E. delegatensis*) leading to stand replacement (Ashton 2000). The recovery of such forests depends on
147 seed dispersal (Whelan 1995). Conversely, resprouters are dominated by species (e.g. *E. radiata*, *E. obliqua*) that
148 mostly survive high intensity fires by developing a thick, hard, and fibrous bark to protect the cambium for
149 reaching lethal temperatures (Gill 1997). Such species respond to fire by sending out epicormic (from the
150 defoliated canopy) or lignotuber shoots in addition to seeding (Gill 1981). However, even for forests dominated
151 by the most fire tolerant resprouter species, stand replacement may occur under extreme intensity fires which kill
152 mature trees (Benyon and Lane 2013) and decrease the amount of viable seeds (under extreme heat conditions
153 most seeds become unviable (Ashton 1986)). A detailed description of fire regimes in such forests can be found
154 in (Fairman et al. in press).

155 2.2 United States

156 The second study area was the west coast of US, stretching south to north from California to Washington. In
157 California, the forest affected by the Iron Complex fire was dominated by a mix of softwood and hardwood
158 western tree species. According to the US Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) database, over 80 % of the trees

159 sampled within the fire perimeter belonged to *Pseudotsuga menziesii*, *Arbutus* sp. or *Quercus chrysolepis*
160 species. The average above ground biomass for the FIA plots located within 30 km of Iron Complex fire was 266
161 t ha⁻¹ (Miles 2014). The mean tree height varied between 9 and 33 m depending on species, with individual trees
162 reaching up to 64 m for *Pseudotsuga menziesii* (Table 1). The mean tree diameter at breast height varied
163 between 18 and 67 cm for the main species. In Oregon, the forest affected by the Rooster Rock fire was
164 dominated by *Pinus ponderosa*, *Pinus contorta* and *Pseudotsuga menziesii* which represented about 60% of the
165 trees, with *Abies alba* and *Alnus rubra* representing an additional 14% of the trees. The average above ground
166 biomass for the FIA plots located within 15 km of the Rooster Rock fire was 84 t ha⁻¹ (Miles 2014). Mean tree
167 height varied from 13 to 27 m depending on species, with individual trees reaching up to 67 m for *Pseudotsuga*
168 *menziesii*. The mean tree diameter at breast height varied between 20 and 42 cm for the main species. In
169 Washington State, the forest affected by the Columbia River Road fire was dominated by *Pinus ponderosa*,
170 *Pinus contorta*, and *Pseudotsuga menziesii* which represented about 65% of the trees, with *Abies lasiocarpa* and
171 *Larix occidentalis* representing additional 16% of the trees. The average above ground biomass for the FIA plots
172 located within 30 km of the Columbia River Road fire was 69 t ha⁻¹ (Miles 2014). Mean tree height varied from
173 11 to 20 m depending on species, with individual trees reaching up to 46 m for *Pseudotsuga menziesii*. The mean
174 tree diameter at breast height varied between 14 and 34 cm for the main species. Although the main species
175 present within the fire perimeter at Rooster Rock and Columbia River Road were similar, the two forests were
176 considered as different types due to the lower biomass level and the shorter, thinner trees present within the fire
177 perimeter at Columbia River Road. Note that only plots sampled before fire from the FIA database were used to
178 compute height and diameter at breast height and that all measurements were transformed to the metric system.

179 Fire regime in *P. menziesii* dominated forests of the Pacific Northwest changes from north to south. In western
180 Washington and Oregon, fires are generally large, infrequent, and severe resulting in extensive even-aged stands
181 (Franklin 1988; Hemstrom and Franklin 1982). Such high severity fires kill most trees, with forest regeneration
182 occurring over extended periods due to the lack of seeds sources or competition with the understory vegetation
183 (Huff 1995; Means 1982). In the dry northwest California, mixed forests dominated by *P. menziesii* and *Q.*
184 *chrysolepis* are characterized by fire return intervals of 13-22 years, with shorter intervals being encountered for
185 south-facing slopes (Agee 1991; Wills and Stuart 1994). Thus, fire regimes in northwest California are different

186 from those in Oregon and Washington, with fires being more frequent and less severe. Such fires kill only some
187 of the overstory trees and create multi-aged stands where tree establishment is associated to higher severity areas
188 killing parts of the canopy (Taylor and Skinner 1998).

189 2.3 Spain

190 The third study area was located in Aragón autonomous region, northeastern Spain (Fig. 1). Out of the three
191 selected fires, two (i.e., Aliaga and los Olmos) were located in the southern part of Aragón in Teruel province,
192 while the third one (Zuera) was located in the central part of Aragón, Zaragoza province. One forest type was
193 considered as being representative for all fires, i.e., pine forests in a Mediterranean semi-arid environment, since
194 the main tree species present at each fire location was the same (i.e., *Pinus halepensis*). The mean plot biomass
195 ranges between 15 t ha⁻¹ and 37 t ha⁻¹ for the Zaragoza and Teruel provinces. The mean tree height was 7 to 9 m,
196 with individual trees reaching up to 15-20 m. The mean tree diameter at breast height was about 20 cm. Data on
197 tree species and forest structure were extracted from the third Spanish Forest National Inventory (FNI)
198 conducted between December 2004 and April 2005.

199 *P. halepensis* forests are the most abundant pine forests in the Mediterranean basin. Fire is an important factor
200 for their maintenance. Such forests are very flammable due to their high density, the presence of branches all
201 along the stem, and the few silvicultural treatments, all of which facilitate large stand replacing fires (Pausas et
202 al. 2008). The fire regime of these ecosystems is characterized by high intensity fire events, with an average
203 occurrence interval of approximately 30 to 50 years (Agee 1998; Arianoutsou and Ne'eman 2000). Such events
204 stimulate recruitment because of increased seed dispersal from the canopy seed bank (Pausas et al. 2008).
205 Despite the high post-fire resilience, regeneration of these pines forests may fail when time intervals between
206 fires are shorter than the time required to accumulate a sufficient seed bank (Márcia et al. 2006).

207 3. Methods

208 The underlying assumptions of this study were that: i) L-band backscatter results from major contributions from
209 the crown layer (mostly branches) and tree stems (Burgin et al. 2011; Dobson et al. 1992; Le Toan et al. 1992);
210 ii) the overstory and plot fire severity are correlated (Tanase et al. 2011); and iii) CBI scores contain information
211 related to fuel consumption (Boby et al. 2010). For this study, fire severity refers to the above ground organic

212 material loss and not to the ecosystem responses associated with fires, such as soil erosion or vegetation recovery
213 (Keeley 2009). Additionally, the CBI was assumed to largely represent fire severity, since factors related to
214 ecosystem responses (e.g. resprouting, seedling colonization) are not assessed for the overstory strata and their
215 influence on the total CBI score (plot level) is low (i.e., factors representing ecosystem responses are few and the
216 averaging process diminishes their influence on the total plot score).

217 3.1 Field data and CBI computation

218 3.1.1 Australia

219 In Australia, field estimates of fire severity were collected between March and July 2009 by DEPI using a
220 specific field protocol developed for the Australian forest conditions. Among other, information on the
221 percentage of green, black and brown tree canopy was recorded for two tree strata together with information on
222 char height. This information was used to compute the CBI scores for these two strata. For the substrate only
223 information on soil and rock cover was collected. Such information was scored according to the CBI protocol and
224 was used to derive a CBI score for the substrate. The CBI at plot level was subsequently computed as the average
225 score of the three available layers. Field protocols used in Australia differed from the CBI protocol defined by
226 Key and Benson (2006). In Australia, field crews did not record information on canopy mortality and substrate
227 fuel consumption. Therefore, although CBI scores computed for the tallest tree strata comprising the overstory
228 layer should be largely similar with what would have been obtained using the standard CBI field protocol (i.e.,
229 canopy mortality is largely incorporated by assessing the percentage of green, black and scorched canopy), for the
230 remaining strata CBI values might differ significantly. Since no information on herbs and low shrubs strata was
231 collected during the field work, the CBI score at plot level might be biased towards representing the canopy fire
232 severity. In total, 552 field plots were available for the analysis, 132 for wet forest, 198 for damp forest and 222
233 for forby forests.

234 3.1.2. United States

235 Field estimates of fire severity were collected in the framework of FIRE SEVerity mapping tools project
236 (FIRESEV) funded by the US Joint Fire Sciences Program. The FIRESEV database includes information on plot
237 location, tree species and canopy characteristics, pre- and post-burn estimates of vegetation in each stratum, CBI

238 values calculated by strata as well as a composite CBI value for the entire plot and field photographs (Sikkink et
239 al. 2013). The data were collected between 2009 and 2011 using a slightly modified CBI field protocol (Dillon
240 et al. 2011). FIRESEV protocol records most of the parameters defined by Key and Benson (2006), although
241 their field assessment might be slightly different. Some parameters, such as the percentage of torched and
242 scorched canopy, were recorded as one (i.e., Black/Brown), while new parameters were added (i.e., diameter of
243 smallest branch left). Therefore CBI scores may present small differences when compared to the original CBI
244 scores. In total, 52 plots were available for the Iron Complex fire, 35 for the Rooster Rock fire, and 40 for the
245 Columbia River Road fire. In addition to the FIRESEV plots, a series of random plots representing unchanged
246 forest conditions were selected outside each fire perimeter.

247 3.1.3 Spain

248 For the Spanish study area, fire severity assessment was conducted within two months after each fire using the
249 CBI field protocol as defined by Key and Benson (2006). At each sample site, the fire severity was evaluated
250 within a 15 m radius using the magnitude of the environmental change with respect to the presumed pre-fire
251 state. The plots were located in areas of homogeneous forest structure and fire effects. The vegetation layers
252 consisted of substrate, herbs and low shrubs less than 1 m tall, shrubs and trees up to 5 m tall (understory layer),
253 and intermediate trees up to 20 m tall (overstory layer). In total, 45 plots were analyzed for the Aliaga fire, 34 for
254 Los Olmos fire, and 123 for the Zuera fire.

255 3.1.4 Fire severity levels

256 Fires had comparable effects across severity levels in all forest sites, with increasing severity translating into
257 increased vegetation removal for different strata (Fig. 2):

- 258 • In low severity areas ($CBI \leq 1$) the litter was partially consumed while the shrub layer was affected in a
259 patchy pattern with the foliage being scorched or partially consumed. Trees could be scorched at the base but
260 tree crowns remained largely unaffected.
- 261 • In moderate severity areas ($1 < CBI \leq 2$), the needles/leaves and small branches of shrubs were
262 consumed or scorched and tree crowns were partially scorched, which resulted in incomplete foliage loss. For

263 moderate–high severity areas ($2 < \text{CBI} \leq 2.5$), the consumption of the understory layer increased, whereas tree
264 crowns were usually scorched, with the foliage being retained only partially. The loss of branches and small
265 twigs was generally small for the highest tree layer.

266 • In high severity areas ($\text{CBI} > 2.5$), the combustion of litter, understory layer, and tree crown elements
267 (i.e., needles and twigs) was usually high, while at the highest severities, small- and medium-sized branches
268 could also be consumed. In some areas within the Kinglake fire extreme fire intensities resulted in strong
269 vertical convection currents which toppled standing trees.

270 In this study, we used the CBI values for the plot level as well as the CBI values for the overstory strata. The
271 overstory fire severity represented the average value of the factors scored within the highest tree strata present at
272 each field sampled location (e.g. percentage of green/black/brown foliage, canopy mortality and char height).
273 This strata was considered the top overstory layer and thus was expected to have the most influence on the radar
274 signal.

275 3.2 Remote sensing data and the Radar Burn Ration (RBR)

276 3.2.1 Radar datasets

277 Between six and nine ALOS PALSAR fine beam dual (FBD, HH and HV polarizations) datasets acquired up to
278 three years before and after the fire event were used for each fire in Spain and US. Due to the size of the
279 Australian fire, FBD data from two adjacent images (identified as West and East in Appendix A) were needed to
280 cover its entire fire perimeter. For Kinglake East, fine beam single (FBS, HH polarization) data were also used
281 due to the lack of FBD data acquired under dry conditions. All SAR datasets were acquired with an incidence
282 angle of 39° at swath center. The acquisition dates together with the environmental conditions at acquisition
283 (precipitation and accumulated precipitation) are presented in Appendix A for each fire. Note that for temperate
284 environments, the spatial variability of soil moisture in the top few centimeters (affecting L-band scattering)
285 should be low during summer due to high air temperatures (high evapotranspiration potential) and low
286 precipitation. Therefore, information on accumulated precipitation for a three day interval prior to the SAR
287 acquisition should reflect the environmental conditions (dry or wet), which further relate to radar signal spatial
288 variability induced by eventual changes in soil surface moisture. Out of the 72 available SAR datasets, three

289 were excluded from the analysis (marked as not used–“nu”) since they were acquired during the fire events. For
290 the Kinglake fire, most of the datasets were acquired under wet conditions. Only two post-fire datasets (marked
291 as dry date – “dd”) were acquired under dry conditions. For the remaining fires the SAR datasets were acquired
292 mostly under dry conditions.

293 All ALOS PALSAR datasets were delivered in single look complex (SLC) format. The SLC data, acquired from
294 the same orbital path at each location, were co-registered using as reference the first image of each data series.
295 Offsets with respect to the reference image were automatically collected for the remaining images using a cross-
296 correlation algorithm (Werner et al. 2005). The offsets were modeled using least-squares regression and a third
297 degree polynomial function that was subsequently used to correct a lookup table used to co-register each image
298 to the reference image. After co-registration, each image was multi-looked in range (4) and azimuth (20) to
299 obtain a ground pixel spacing of approximately 60 m. SAR intensity was transformed to the radar backscatter
300 coefficient (σ^0) after applying polarization specific absolute calibration factors (Shimada et al. 2009). The final
301 SAR pre-processing step was orthorectification to the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection using a
302 lookup table based on digital elevation model (DEM) and the orbital information of the SAR data. To correct for
303 possible inaccuracies in the input data, a refinement of the lookup table was applied in form of offsets between
304 the reference SAR image and a DEM-based simulated SAR image transformed to the radar geometry
305 (Wegmüller et al. 2002). For the Australian fire the 30 m spacing Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM)
306 digital elevation model (DEM) was used. The SRTM DEM was enhanced at Geoscience Australia by removing
307 artifacts and noise present in the original SRTM data (Gallant et al. 2011). For the Spanish study area a 20 m
308 DEM obtained from the regional government of Aragón was used, while for the U.S. study areas a 30 m DEM
309 from the US National Elevation Dataset (NED) was used (<http://ned.usgs.gov>).

310 3.2.2 The Radar Burn Ratio

311 The Radar Burn Ratio (RBR) involved the computation of post- to pre-fire ratio of the backscattering
312 coefficients in power units (1).

$$313 \quad RBR_{xy} = \text{Postfire average backscatter}_{xy} / \text{Prefire average backscatter}_{xy} \quad (1)$$

314 where: xy represents a specific polarization (or radar based index)

315 RBR was calculated for each polarization (i.e., HH and HV) and for the radar forest degradation index (RFDI)
316 (2) which expresses the strength of the double bounce term and direct soil backscattering (Mitchard et al. 2011).

$$317 \quad \text{RFDI} = (\text{HH} - \text{HV}) / (\text{HH} + \text{HV}) \quad (2)$$

318 where: HH and HV represent the backscattering coefficient in power units

319 RBR indices were computed as the average post-fire backscatter among several post-fire images divided by the
320 average pre-fire backscatter among several pre-fire images (RBR_{HH} , RBR_{HV} , and RBR_{RFDI}) with two exceptions:
321 for the Rooster Rock and Kinglake fires, only one post-fire image was available or was acquired under dry
322 conditions. In these cases, the RBRs were computed as the single date post-fire backscatter divided by the pre-
323 fire average backscatter. For Kinglake fire, the RBRs were also computed using the average post-fire images
324 acquired under wet conditions. The use of pre- and post-fire averages was deemed to better represent average
325 forest conditions by removing the stochastic part of the signal. Such an approach is similar to multi-temporal
326 filtering (Quegan et al. 2000). Temporal filtering consists of exploiting the signatures of a scatterer in multiple
327 images and it can be referred to as multi-looking in the temporal domain. For undisturbed forests, multi-temporal
328 backscatter averages provide more accurate values by filtering out random temporal variations, i.e., forest
329 structure is largely stable. In disturbed forests the backscatter signal is affected not only by the remaining
330 vegetation, i.e., fire-impact dependent, but also by the forest recovery processes, i.e., recruitment and regrowth.
331 However, for the studied coniferous forests post-fire regrowth is slow. In Mediterranean pine forests seedlings
332 reach only 15-20 cm 39 months after fires (Thanos et al. 1996) while in temperate coniferous forests saplings
333 reach only 81 cm 11 years after fires (Turner et al. 2004). Since L-band backscatter is mostly influenced by large
334 vegetation components such as branches and trunks (Le Toan et al. 1992), low vegetation has a limited influence
335 on the post-fire radar signal during the first years after fire. In addition, for intermediate and low severity levels,
336 the unburnt vegetation is likely to mask out the effects of recruitment/regrowth over the first years. Therefore, a
337 three year gap is unlikely to significantly affect post-fire backscatter values in slow growing forests. However,
338 the post-fire acquisition gap of radar datasets may need to be limited in faster growing forests (e.g., for eucalypt
339 forest the reported growth rates are higher, (Van Der Meer et al. 1999)) to avoid mixing the two concurring

340 effects (fire impact and forest recovery). Note that by using post- to pre-fire ratios the effect of topography on
341 the radar signal is mathematically cancelled out and therefore topographic normalization is not necessary.

342 3.3 Estimation of fire severity using the Radar Burn Ratio

343 This section was structured in three parts. First, relationships between field estimates of fire severity from CBI
344 plots and RBRs (i.e., SAR backscatter change) were studied and fire severity was estimated for each fire through
345 local empirical modeling (LEM) as explained in section 3.3.1. Second, several sets of thresholds for the
346 standardized RBR indices were produced (section 3.3.2) to assess fire severity: i) a set of ‘common thresholds’
347 derived from all nine forest fires, ii) two sets of ‘species specific thresholds’ derived from fires in coniferous
348 forests (n=5, California forest excluded) and eucalypt forests (n=3), and iii) two sets of ‘environmental
349 conditions thresholds’ derived from wet and dry images for the eucalypt forests. Although one would prefer
350 SAR imagery acquired under dry conditions to assess fire severity effects (i.e., the influence of soil moisture
351 spatial variability is low), it was deemed necessary to also compute thresholds for wet conditions since in
352 eucalypt forests dry conditions at image acquisition were rare (just one post-fire dataset). However, note that
353 under such environmental conditions the variability in SAR image is not related only to fire effects. Third, fire
354 severity was estimated for all fires applying the standardized RBR thresholds (standardized models - SM) as
355 explained in section 3.3.3. The comparison between the accuracy of LEM and SM methods was carried out by
356 assessing the agreement between the predicted and the observed fire severity.

357 3.3.1 Empirical modeling of fire severity

358 Fire severity was estimated through local empirical models calibrated for each fire. Such models related field
359 estimates of fire severity to remote sensing data extracted for the pixel coordinates corresponding to the center of
360 each CBI plot for each ratio (RBR_{HH} , RBR_{HV} , and RBR_{RFDI}) and fire. The relationship between fire severity and
361 RBRs was studied through scatterplots, while the coefficient of determination (R^2) was used to understand the
362 proportion of RBR variability explained by changes in fire severity. Fire severity retrieval was carried out using
363 regression-based modeling with cross-validation. Empirical models relating fire severity at plot or overstory
364 levels with RBR indices were developed and tested for each of the nine fires. For the Australian fire, separate
365 models were developed for the dry and wet conditions. Due to the relatively low number of field samples

366 available for most fires, cross-validation was based on bootstrapping. Through an iterative process each sample
367 was removed from the training dataset when calibrating the regression model and subsequently its difference
368 with the modeled value was computed. These differences were used to compute one-factor-at-a-time root mean
369 squared error (RMSE) as the root of the average squared difference between the observed and the predicted
370 values obtained during the iterative process. Additionally, model R^2 (computed using all observations) and the
371 correlation between predicted and observed values (r , computed using the set aside independent samples during
372 the iterative cross-validation) were used to characterize the goodness of fit for each RBR index under dry or wet
373 conditions (Australian fire only). The agreement between observed and predicted fire severity was evaluated
374 using Cohen's weighted kappa (Cohen 1968) after reclassifying the continuous CBI interval into five classes:
375 unchanged ($CBI=0$), low severity ($0 < CBI \leq 1$), medium severity ($1 < CBI \leq 2$), medium-high severity ($2 < CBI \leq 2.5$),
376 and high severity ($CBI > 2.5$). These classes generally correspond to the CBI field protocol as defined by Key and
377 Benson (2006). Cohen's kappa is a conservative measure of agreement between two classifications that takes
378 into account the agreement occurring by chance. The weighted kappa is useful when classes are ordered (e.g.,
379 unchanged to high severity) by taking into account the seriousness of disagreement through a weight matrix
380 (Cohen 1968). Kappa values are affected by factors other than agreement (e.g., number of classes) and thus no
381 one value can be regarded as universally acceptable (Bakeman et al. 1997; Sim and Wright 2005). However,
382 some magnitude guidelines were provided in the literature (Landis and Koch 1977): no agreement (negative
383 kappa), slight agreement (0-0.20), fair agreement (0.21-0.40), moderate agreement (0.41-.60), substantial
384 agreement (0.61-0.80) and almost perfect agreement (0.81-1.0).

385 3.3.2 Defining standardized RBR cut thresholds using *a priori* information from CBI plots

386 Field data needed for local calibration of empirical models are often unavailable or obtained at significant cost.
387 Therefore, estimating fires severity without *a priori* information on local burn conditions is important for a wide
388 range of objectives. This could be achieved by calibrating a set of cut thresholds for remote sensing indices (e.g.
389 thresholds on dNBR (Key and Benson (2006))). Such calibration is commonly carried out using field datasets. A
390 robust set of thresholds needs to consider the range of burn conditions present within a fire perimeter (i.e., fire
391 severity), variations in burn conditions across landscapes occupied by a mix of forest species, forest structures

392 and fire regimes as well as variations in environmental (e.g., rainfall) or local conditions (e.g., topography). Such
 393 variations result in different RBR ranges (see Section 4.1), which in turn hinder fire severity retrieval using
 394 algorithms based on change values in absolute scale. The influence of environmental conditions is minimized by
 395 an appropriate selection of the radar datasets (dry vs. wet), while topographic effects are eliminated through the
 396 use of change detection approaches (i.e. post- to pre-fire ratios). Compensating for varying RBR ranges across
 397 landscapes can be achieved by statistical data standardization, which constrains the RBR values to specific
 398 scales. A standard score (z) is a dimensionless number (positive or negative) representing the distance between
 399 the initial value and the population mean (3). Z-scores range between ± 4 with 95% of the values being within ± 2
 400 for a normally distributed population ($\alpha=0.05$) and are calculated as follows:

$$401 \quad z = (x - \mu) / \sigma \quad (3)$$

402 where: μ and σ are the mean and standard deviation of the population respectively.

403 Standardization was carried out separately for each fire using RBR values extracted at CBI plot locations. First,
 404 the mean RBR ($\bar{x}_{RBR-Fire \cdot SeverityClass}$) was computed by severity class for each fire (4), i.e., unchanged, low,
 405 moderate, moderate-high and high as follows:

$$406 \quad \bar{x}_{RBR-Fire \cdot SeverityClass \ i} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n RBR_{Fire \ j \cdot SeverityClass \ i}}{n} \quad (4)$$

407 where: j refers to each of the nine fires, i refers to each of the five severity classes and k refers to the
 408 number of CBI plots in each combination of fire and severity class.

409 Stratifying by fire severity classes assumed that CBI plots were representative of the variable burn conditions
 410 within each class. Stratifying removes the influence of the area extent of individual severity classes on the mean
 411 RBR value at fire level, avoiding bias caused by unequal sampling among fire severity classes in most fires.
 412 Based on the mean RBR values by severity class ($\bar{x}_{RBR-Fire \cdot SeverityClass}$), the fire-wide mean ($\mu_{RBR-Fire}$) and standard
 413 deviation ($\sigma_{RBR-Fire}$) were computed for each fire (eqs. 5 and 6) and subsequently used to produce the
 414 standardized scores (7):

415
$$\mu_{RBR \cdot Fire j} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^5 \bar{x}_{RBR \cdot Fire j \cdot Severity Class i}}{5} \quad (5)$$

416
$$\sigma_{RBR \cdot Fire j} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^5 (\bar{x}_{RBR \cdot Fire j \cdot Severity Class i} - \mu_{RBR \cdot Fire j})^2}{(5 - 1)}} \quad (6)$$

417
$$Z_{RBR \cdot Fire j \cdot Severity Class i} = \frac{(\bar{x}_{RBR \cdot Fire j \cdot Severity Class i} - \mu_{RBR \cdot Fire j})}{\sigma_{RBR j}} \quad (7)$$

418 Following standardization, scores for each severity class were obtained (at plot and overstory levels) for each
 419 fire and environmental condition (dry and wet). The standard scores were averaged across fires ($Z_{RBR \cdot Severity Class}$)
 420 by severity classes (eq. 8) and were subsequently used (together with the standard error, $\alpha=0.05$) to determine
 421 the upper and lower variation limits for each severity class:

422
$$Z_{RBR \cdot Severity Class i} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m Z_{RBR \cdot Fire j \cdot Severity Class i}}{m} \quad (8)$$

423 where: m is the number of fires used to calculate the Common thresholds (i.e., all fires, m=9), Species
 424 specific thresholds (i.e. fires in coniferous forest, m=5, and eucalypt forest, m=3) and Environmental conditions
 425 thresholds (i.e. dry m=3, and wet m=3, for eucalypt forests only).

426 The last step was computing the standardized RBR cut thresholds for fire severity mapping by averaging the
 427 upper and respectively lower limits of adjacent fire severity classes. One should notice that wet conditions scores
 428 were based on data from Kinglake fire and therefore applicable only to eucalypt forests.

429 3.3.3 Applying standardized RBR cut thresholds without *a priori* information – Standardized models
 430 (SM)

431 Once common standardized RBR cut thresholds are defined, a straightforward process allows for mapping fire
 432 severity across landscapes by applying the cut thresholds to the standardized RBR pixel values. The most
 433 problematic step is determining μ and σ for standardization without *a priori* information on fire severity from
 434 field plots. This was achieved by extracting RBR values for all pixels within each fire perimeter, filtering the
 435 values by eliminating outliers i.e., values below and above the 1st and the 99th percentile, and computing the

436 mean values of five intervals equally spaced between the minimum and the maximum RBR. Such intervals
437 might not correspond directly to pre-defined severity classes (e.g., from CBI data) but they would correspond to
438 different severity levels due to the linear relationship between RBR and fire severity as shown in the following
439 sections. The advantage of such an approach is that the mean of these interval means (fire-wide μ) and standard
440 deviation (σ) are not area dependent (i.e., usually fire severity classes are not equally represented and thus the
441 mean backscatter values over a fire perimeter depends on the number of pixels falling within each severity
442 class). Using μ and σ , each pixel was standardized (as in eq. 1) and the previously computed standardized RBR
443 cut thresholds were applied to estimate the fire severity class at each pixel. The agreement between the fire
444 severity class computed through the standardized model was cross-checked against field data using Cohen's
445 weighted kappa after reclassifying the continuous CBI interval into five severity classes (see section 3.3.1).

446 4. Results

447 For all fires the ground assessed CBI ranged between 0 (not burned) and 3 (high fire severity) at both overstory
448 and plot levels. For the Australian fire approximately 30% of the forest was assessed at high fire severities with
449 further 41% being assessed at medium severities (Cruz et al. 2012). In wet forests (dominated by *E. regnans* and
450 *E. delegatensis*) high fire severities resulted in widespread tree mortality, while at low fire severities trees largely
451 survived. For damp and forby forests (i.e., dominated by fire tolerant species such as *E. radiata* and *E. obliqua*)
452 tree survival was high (above 90%) at high and intermediate fire severities (Benyon and Lane 2013). For the
453 Spanish fires large areas were affected by stand replacing fires. At medium and high fire severities coniferous
454 trees were generally killed, since foliage was usually scorched or incinerated. In such areas understory mortality
455 was also widespread (Tanase et al. 2011). According to the Monitoring Trends in Burn Severity (MTBS) project
456 maps the areas affected by medium and high fire severities in the US were 33%, 72% and 37% for Iron
457 Complex, Rooster Rock, and Columbia River Road fires, respectively (Eidenshink et al. 2007). The correlation
458 between field assessed overstory and plot fire severity was high ($r>0.9$) for all forests dominated by coniferous
459 species. For mixed species forests (i.e., Iron Complex fire) the correlation between plot and overstory severity
460 was lower ($r=0.74$). For eucalypt forests the plot fire severity was largely based on information collected for tree
461 strata, making the correlation with overstory fire severity high as expected ($r>0.9$).

462 4.1 Relationships between RBR indices and fire severity – Local empirical models

463 The relationship between RBRs and field estimated fire severity was assessed for each fire separately. For all
464 fires a linear relationship was observed between fire severity and RBR. Figure 3 reports the trend in RBR_{HV} and
465 RBR_{RFDI} with fire severity under dry environmental conditions. For the Kinglake fire individual trends for each
466 forest type are plotted. For unchanged areas, values around 1 (0 dB change) were observed, as expected. With
467 increasing fire severity RBR_{HV} decreased since vegetation scattering reduces due to combustion of scattering
468 elements (mostly leaves and branches and occasionally stems). For RBR_{HH} (not shown) a similar trend was
469 observed, while an opposite trend was observed for RBR_{RFDI} . Increasing RBR_{RFDI} with fire severity was the
470 result of higher post-fire RFDI values. Higher post-fire RFDI values were explained by a differentiated effect of
471 fire severity on HH and respectively HV polarizations, with HH backscatter decrease due to removal of
472 scattering elements being compensated by increased surface scattering. Such an effect is not present for the
473 volume dominated HV polarization, which explains the increasing post-fire RFDI with fire severity. The RBR
474 dynamic range from unburnt (unchanged) to high severity levels varied across fires. For the RBR_{HV} polarization
475 the signal decreased by about 8 dB for the Zuera fire (dB values were obtained by multiplying the logarithm of
476 the ratios to base 10 by 10). For most other fires the change at the highest severity was about 3.5 dB. The
477 exception was the Iron Complex fire, for which the change was approximately 1.5 dB. For RBR_{HH} (not shown)
478 the change was lower (about 2.2 dB), reaching a maximum of about 4 dB for the Zuera fire. For RBR_{RFDI} the
479 post-fire signal increased by about 1 dB with a maximum for the Zuera fire (2 dB) and a minimum for the Iron
480 complex fire (0.4 dB). A more detailed depiction of RBR_{HV} trend as a function of fire severity is presented in
481 Figure S1 for dry environmental conditions. The figure shows scatterplots of RBR_{HV} as a function of CBI values
482 within each fire. It also presents the strength of the relationships using the coefficient of determination from
483 linear regression modeling. It is evident from Figure S1 that similar fire severity levels as expressed through CBI
484 resulted in a range of values independently of forest type (i.e., notice the RBR_{HV} variability around the
485 regression lines). Under wet environmental conditions RBR_{HV} presented no sensitivity to fire severity (the slope
486 was close to zero) while RBR_{HH} had an inverse trend, (i.e., values increased with increasing fire severity due to
487 the enhanced signal from a moist surface coupled with a reduced attenuation due to vegetation combustion). The
488 RBR_{RFDI} trend did not change from dry to wet conditions. In general, under wet conditions the variation from

489 unchanged to high severity class was slightly lower, with the radar signal increasing by about 1.8 dB and 0.8 dB
490 for RBR_{HH} and respectively RBR_{RFDI} .

491 Error metrics (i.e., R^2 , r , RMSE and kappa) for local empirical models developed from RBR_{HV} for each
492 individual fire are presented in Fig. 4, while scatterplots of the observed vs. predicted values are shown in Fig. 5
493 for both plot and overstory severity levels. Detailed information on such metrics for each RBR index and
494 environmental conditions is provided in Table 2, along with information on model bias. Overall, the highest
495 agreement (i.e., kappa) and model coefficient of determination (R^2) and the lowest estimation error (i.e., RMSE)
496 were observed for the overstory layer, which is not unexpected since the radar signal is mostly influenced by the
497 upper part of the canopy. Kappa, R^2 , and r values were between 0.06 and 0.1 higher while RMSE was about 0.08
498 lower when estimating overstory fire severity under dry environmental conditions. Under wet conditions such
499 differences were marginal. Under dry environmental conditions, the RBR index most sensitive to fire severity
500 was RBR_{HV} followed by RBR_{HH} and RBR_{RFDI} . However, under wet conditions RBR_{RFDI} was slightly better when
501 compared to RBR_{HH} . When comparing the two environmental conditions (Australian fire only) kappa, R^2 , r and
502 RMSE values were generally worse for wet dates particularly for the overstory layer.

503 4.2 Relationship between RBR indices and fire severity - Standardized models

504 The standardization of backscatter change for individual fires allowed for obtaining a similar data range for each
505 RBR index, as exemplified in Fig. 6 for dry environmental conditions and plot fire severity (RBR_{HV} and
506 RBR_{RFDI}). In Fig. 6, standardized RBR varies between approximately 1.5 and -1.5 from unchanged to high fire
507 severity levels in all fires. It is evident, when comparing to Fig. 2, that the spread of value among fires was
508 lower, particularly for RBR_{HV} , and that the trend as a function of fire severity was maintained.

509 The ability of the standardized RBR_{HV} index to discriminate among fire severity classes is shown in Fig. 7 for
510 plot and overstory levels. Fig. 7 shows that standardized RBR_{HV} values and confidence intervals do not overlap,
511 which should translate into a reliable estimation of fire class severity using the computed cut thresholds (Table
512 3). The main difference between plot and overstory fire severity was the trend with severity, which is linear for
513 the overstory layer. At the plot level the trend with fire severity is linear only for moderate to high severity
514 classes and starts to flatten out for low severity and unchanged areas. Such differences were not unexpected,

515 since fire severity at the plot level does not always linearly relate to overstory fire severity, particularly in tall
516 forests where surface fires do not always reach forest canopy. For some RBR indices, environmental conditions
517 or severity levels confidence intervals of adjacent severity classes overlapped (Figures S2 to S4), suggesting that
518 the estimated fire severity is less reliable for those conditions. Under dry conditions, the RBR_{HV} index was least
519 affected by such problems, while under wet conditions, RBR_{RFDI} showed significantly less overlap between
520 adjacent severity classes when compared to RBR_{HH} (Figure S4).

521 The agreement between observed and estimated fires severity using standardized models (i.e., cut thresholds) is
522 provided in Table 4. On average, substantial agreement ($\kappa=0.67-0.69$) was observed between fire severity
523 estimates based on RBR_{HV} and field data. For RBR_{HH} and RBR_{RFDI} the agreement was moderate ($\kappa=0.45-$
524 0.53) and fair ($0.36-0.39$) respectively under dry environmental conditions. Under wet conditions RBR_{HH} and
525 RBR_{RFDI} based severity provided only fair and respectively moderate agreement ($\kappa = 0.30-0.45$).

526 When comparing the kappa values obtained using common cut thresholds vs. species specific thresholds (Fig. 8,
527 left panel), it was evident that only a marginal improvement of the estimation accuracy was obtained when using
528 the latter, i.e., kappa increased by about 0.01 with a maximum of 0.1 for eucalypt forests and RBR_{RFDI} .
529 Differences were generally higher for RBR_{HH} and RBR_{RFDI} for overstory fire severity. However, a clear pattern
530 was not evident, with kappa values for some fires being higher when using common thresholds.

531 Overall, kappa values for plot and overstory layers were similar, with a marginal improvement towards the latter
532 (Table 4). When analyzing by individual fires, for 40% of the cases kappa values were higher by at least 0.1
533 when estimating fire severity at the overstory layer while for about 30% of the cases the opposite was true for
534 RBR_{HV} . For the remaining 30% of the cases kappa differences between plot and overstory layers were below 0.1.
535 For RBR_{HH} and RBR_{RFDI} a difference in kappa (plot vs. overstory) over 0.1 was observed for only 10% of the
536 cases under dry conditions while under wet conditions the percentage was even lower. The highest agreement
537 with the observed fire severity was obtained using RBR_{HV} , followed by RBR_{HH} and RBR_{RFDI} .

538 4.3 Local empirical models vs. standardized models for fire severity mapping

539 The comparison between fire severity estimation accuracy (i.e. kappa) using local empirical modeling vs. using
540 standardized models (with common thresholds) is shown in Fig. 8 (right panel) for both plot and overstory

541 levels. Notice the fairly similar results provided by the two methods, particularly for RBR_{HV} and RBR_{HH} . For
542 RBR_{RFDI} empirical modelling provided more accurate fire severity estimation (higher kappa values). Overall, in
543 about 10% of the cases local empirical models provided kappa values at least 0.1 higher, while the opposite was
544 true (at least 0.1 lower) for about 15% of the cases. For RBR_{HV} , plot severity was more accurately estimated
545 using standardized models with common thresholds. Contrarily, overstory severity was better estimated when
546 using local empirical models. However, the average difference in kappa values between the two methods was
547 well below 0.1 for RBR_{HV} . Under wet environmental conditions the average kappa was marginally higher when
548 using standardized models with common thresholds.

549 The spatial representation of overstory fire severity as estimated using common thresholds on RBR_{HV} for dry
550 acquisition is provided in Fig. 9. Notice the detection of additional fire scars from previous years (close to
551 Columbia River Road fire) as well as areas detected outside fire perimeters (e.g. Kinglake fire) caused by inter-
552 annual changes of cropping areas. Such areas are largely filtered out when using multi-temporal filtering as
553 shown for the remaining fires.

554 5. Discussion

555 5.1 The Radar Burn Ratio (RBR): a change detection framework

556 Previous studies showed that L-band is the most sensitive wavelength to fire effects and its sensitivity does not
557 change significantly across a range of environments, such as Mediterranean and boreal forest (Tanase et al.
558 2010a; Tanase et al. 2010b). Such studies used locally calibrated empirical models to relate post-fire radar data
559 to field or remote estimates (i.e., from optical indices) of fire severity. However, models based on post-fire
560 datasets need to account for variations in the local incidence angle, which had a significant influence on the
561 sensitivity to fire effects, particularly for steep slopes facing the radar sensor and co-polarized waves (Tanase et
562 al. 2010a). By combining pre- and post-fire SAR datasets within a change detection framework (RBR), the effect
563 of local incidence angle was removed, with the radar signal depending only on the forest condition at any given
564 plot. This allowed for the use of simpler and more robust empirical-models when estimating fire severity. It was
565 further shown by this study that RBR indices showed similar trends over a range of fire regimes. This suggests
566 that models to map fire severity over wide areas can be built without needing costly field data. The similar RBR

567 trends over the range of forest types studied can be attributed to the physical fire effects: increasing fire severity
568 increases the proportion of removed vegetation, which causes similar changes of the radar signal.

569 Overall, the RBR provided a relative measure of fire induced changes, since post-fire information was related to
570 the local pre-fire forest condition at pixel level. The use of pre- and post-fire multi-temporal averages allowed
571 for decreasing pixel-wise speckle noise, which improved fire severity estimation. Indeed, parallel analyses (not
572 shown) revealed that correlations between field estimates of fire severity and RBR indices were in all cases
573 higher when using multi-temporal SAR analysis when compared to single date pre- to post-fire image ratios.
574 RBR effectiveness for fire severity estimation was related to forest structural properties, with its accuracy being
575 reduced in forests with high aboveground biomass. In the particular case of L-band wavelength, a large part of
576 the scattering comes from branches and trunks (Le Toan et al. 1992; McDonald et al. 1990). However, even the
577 most severe fires will often consume just tree leaves and small branches, leaving dead stems standing. This
578 means that differences in total scattering when compared to pre-fire levels (the degree of change), may not vary
579 much across severity classes as scattering from tree trunks may largely replace scattering from branches
580 particularly for high biomass forests. The L-band saturation limit at about 100 t ha^{-1} compromises the strength of
581 the relationship between the SAR signal and biomass in such forests, thus hindering an accurate estimation of
582 changes in SAR scattering. However, it is expected that RBR from SAR sensors with longer wavelengths and
583 thus higher saturation limits (e.g., P-band from the future BIOMASS mission) would provide more accurate
584 results in forests with high levels of biomass.

585 5.2 Fire severity estimation using RBR indices

586 Local empirical calibration of linear regression models showed that fire severity could be estimated accurately
587 for most of the fires, with RBR_{HV} explaining up to 86% of the observed post-fire forest variability at plot or
588 overstory levels (Table 1). On average, RBR_{HV} explained 57% and 65% of the observed post-fire forest
589 variability for plot and canopy levels, respectively. RMSE errors down to 15-20% of the CBI range were
590 observed in this study. However, such results were not uniform and appeared to be related to forest structure.
591 Better results (higher R^2 , r and kappa and lower RMSE) were obtained for forests with average biomass levels
592 well below the L-band saturation limit and with limited species diversity (Aliaga, Los Olmos, Zuera, Rooster

593 Rock and Columbia River Road), particularly from *Pinus* genus. Overall, fire severity estimation in such areas
594 was reasonably high, with R^2 values above 0.6, RMSE errors around 30% and kappa above 0.6 (i.e., substantial
595 classification agreement). For higher biomass forests (i.e., Kinglake and Iron Complex fires) the estimation
596 accuracy decreased, with R^2 values usually below 0.6 and kappa values around 0.5 (moderate agreement). The
597 lowest estimation accuracy was observed for the Iron Complex fire, where softwood and hardwood species were
598 mixed. Particularly, fire severity estimation at the plot level was more problematic. Such results might be
599 explained by the disconnect between fire severity recorded for the highest forest strata and the remaining strata
600 (i.e., $r \approx 0.5$), especially since fire severity estimation for the overstory layer was considerably better. This
601 observation was supported by the results observed for eucalypt forests, which were also better for the overstory
602 layer. Note that for the eucalypt forest, CBI values at plot and overstory levels were similar because limited
603 information on fire effects on the surface and shrub layers was available. This may explain the much closer
604 kappa values obtained for plot and overstory layers for the eucalypt forests when compared to the mixed
605 softwood and hardwood forests. Nevertheless, it is important to note that field reference data were collected
606 using an index (i.e., CBI) specifically designed with optical datasets in mind, e.g., it assesses fire severity from a
607 ‘color’ perspective: percentage of green, black or brown vegetation. Since SAR data are sensitive to the amount
608 of vegetation elements consumed by fire, there is potential in improving the relationship between RBR and fire
609 severity by collecting information on branch/stems consumption within existing or new field protocols.
610 Therefore, more detailed field-based studies that focus on factors measuring fuel consumption would provide a
611 better calibration dataset and thus a more accurate fire severity estimation from RBR indices.

612 When compared to previous work carried out for the Zuera fire using local empirical modeling and post-fire
613 datasets (Tanase et al. 2010a; Tanase et al. 2014b), fire severity estimation using RBR_{HV} was similar, with
614 slightly higher R^2 values being observed in this study i.e., 0.86 vs. 0.78. One should note, however, that previous
615 studies made use of ALOS PALSAR data acquired under wetter conditions, and that reference fire severity were
616 based on dNBR, both of which might have negatively influenced the relationship between fire severity and the
617 post-fire radar dataset.

618 5.3 Mapping fire severity without *a priori* information - the potential of standardized RBR

619 Models based on standardized RBR thresholds provided similar estimation accuracies when compared to local
620 empirical models, particularly for RBR_{HV} and plot severity level. Such results suggested that a common set of
621 thresholds could be used to estimate fire severity over wide areas without the need for *a priori* information. An
622 interesting result was the higher estimation accuracy obtained for the Iron Complex fire when using standardized
623 models for plot severity estimation, i.e., kappa increased from 0.26 to 0.35, which was difficult to explain with
624 the available data. Although species-specific thresholds did not provide significantly better results, future
625 research might demonstrate whether such observation is valid for other forest types. The RBR index based on
626 cross-polarized channel (RBR_{HV}), was the most sensitive to fire severity, corroborating the results of previous
627 studies (Tanase et al. 2010a; Tanase et al. 2014b; Tanase et al. 2010b).

628 Using the standardized RBR cut thresholds proposed in this study, fire severity estimation is straightforward for
629 the range of forest types analyzed, and relatively accurate estimates should be obtained, particularly under dry
630 conditions when using RBR indices based on cross-polarized data. Furthermore, for environments with similar
631 forest types and fire effects (e.g., boreal), the proposed thresholds should produce reasonable results when
632 estimating overstory fire severity, since L-band data sensitivity to fire effects in boreal environments has been
633 already demonstrated (Tanase et al. 2010b). However, applying the proposed standardized RBR cut thresholds to
634 significantly different environments such as tropical must be carried out with caution. Particularly, one should
635 use field data to calibrate a set of specific thresholds using the proposed methodology. Alternatively, at least
636 validation of the results using field estimates of fire severity should be carried when applying the common cut
637 thresholds proposed in this study. Further research is needed to understand the cause of the considerably lower
638 agreement with field data observed for mixed softwood and hardwood forests. Such lower estimation accuracies
639 might have been caused by particular conditions within Iron Complex fire, and may not necessarily represent all
640 mixed species forests.

641 5.4 The influence of environmental conditions on fire severity estimation

642 Environmental conditions affected the ability of RBR indices to relate to fire severity. Previous studies showed
643 that under wet environmental conditions, variations in soil moisture may significantly affect radar backscatter,
644 hindering the retrieval of biophysical forest characteristics in areas affected by fires (Kasischke et al. 2007;

645 Kasischke et al. 2011). Such effects were also observed in this study, with RBR_{HV} showing almost no sensitivity
646 to fire severity in eucalypt forests for which wet environmental conditions at image acquisition were typically
647 encountered. Under dry conditions RBR_{HV} showed the highest sensitivity to fire severity in all forest types. Such
648 limitations may indicate that a careful selection of the post-fire images used to derive RBR indices is needed,
649 particularly in areas where wet conditions predominate. For other forest types, RBR_{HV} computed from data
650 acquired during wetter periods might be sensitive enough to enable fire severity estimation. Such an assumption
651 is supported by previous findings showing that in a Mediterranean environment L-band data acquired under
652 wetter conditions was sensitive to fire effects (Tanase et al. 2010a; Tanase et al. 2014b). Therefore, further
653 studies are needed to clarify the extent to which wet environmental conditions affect fire severity estimation for
654 different forest types.

655 For co-polarized waves wet conditions resulted in completely opposite trends, with RBR_{HH} increasing with fire
656 severity. Such a dramatic change was explained by the dominance of different scattering mechanisms, with
657 volume scattering being completely replaced by dihedral and surface scattering due to increased soil moisture. In
658 such a scenario, a decreased attenuation layer (foliage) would result in increased post-fire surface and dihedral
659 scattering with respect to pre-fire levels. However, despite the change in trend direction, the empirical
660 relationships between RBR_{HH} and fire severity were maintained with R^2 , r , RMSE and kappa value being similar
661 with those obtained under dry environmental conditions (see Table 2). Similarly, for RBR_{RFDI} , the change from
662 dry to wet environmental conditions did not significantly affect the relationship strength with fire severity. Such
663 results suggest that fire severity estimation is possible even under wetter environmental conditions. However, the
664 estimation accuracy is considerably lower when compared to using cross-polarized data acquired under dry
665 environmental conditions.

666 5.5 Applicability to other systems

667 In this study, fire severity was examined through the reduction in the above ground vegetation material of the tree
668 layer strata. Such an approach may prove inadequate when assessing fire severity in areas affected by low
669 severity fires (e.g., sub-canopy tree mortality) or for the direct estimation of litter and organic layer consumption,
670 relevant when assessing fire impacts at plot level in boreal forests (Kasischke et al. 2008). Since L-band SAR is

671 highly sensitive to the reduction of vegetation material within the canopy layer, estimating fire severity over the
672 entire vertical vegetation profile (plot severity) would result in less accurate results when understory and
673 overstory fire effects are not correlated (e.g., in low intensity surface fires tree canopy remains largely intact). In
674 such conditions, L-band radar scattering (dominated by the upper canopy) might not properly represent plot fire
675 severity. Nevertheless, for coniferous dominated forest such scenarios are less common, with the area affected by
676 medium and high severities being usually large. In addition, when trees are relatively short (10 to 20 m height) or
677 for low biomass open canopy forests L-band penetration is sufficiently high and therefore the understory plays a
678 role in the total scattering. High correlation coefficients between overstory and plot severity were observed for all
679 coniferous dominated forests which suggests that indirect estimation of plot severity might be appropriate for
680 some forest types. For other forest types, the accuracy of plot fire severity estimates may largely depend on other
681 indicators (e.g., organic layer depth) which are difficult to appraise from remote sensing data.

682 6 Conclusions

683 This study provides a significant advance of the current knowledge by integrating pre- and post-fire SAR
684 datasets within a change detection approach, and represents the first attempt to derive standardized thresholds for
685 a rapid fire severity mapping from SAR datasets. Using a novel framework, the Radar Burn Ratio was developed
686 for fire severity estimation using field data from seven forest types with above ground biomass values ranging
687 from 30 to over 500 t ha⁻¹. Two retrieval strategies were tested: i) local empirical modeling based on RBR values
688 and, ii) generalized models based on standardized RBR values. Based on the standardized RBR values, common
689 and forest species specific cut thresholds were computed and subsequently used to estimate fire severity without
690 the need for *a priori* information.

691 The study demonstrated that while forest fire regimes might differ, the impact on the radar signal is similar, with
692 RBR showing comparable trends over a wide range of fires. Local empirical models showed that fire severity
693 could be estimated accurately for most fires, particularly in areas with average biomass levels within the L-band
694 sensitivity interval and where plot and overstory fire effects were correlated. For forests with average biomass
695 levels well above the L-band saturation limit, fire severity estimation was achievable at lower accuracies. The
696 RBR index most sensitive to fire severity was based on the cross-polarized channel. The standardized RBR

697 allowed for the estimation of fire severity without *a priori* information and with estimation accuracies similar to
698 those obtained from local empirical models calibrated with in-situ data. The methods proposed in this study are
699 particularly valuable for a rapid estimation of fire severity at regional to global levels once a set of pre-calibrated
700 thresholds are developed for different environments. However, further studies should focus on improving field-
701 based indices (e.g., CBI) to better quantify fuel consumption. Such improved field datasets would increase fire
702 severity estimation from RBR indices due to the direct relationships between the radar signal and the amount of
703 scattering elements in the canopy.

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- 907
- 908 List of Figure Captions
- 909 Fig. 1. Locations of the studied fires showing fire perimeter and the CBI field plots overlaid on pre-fire Landsat images
- 910 Fig. 2 Examples of low (left), moderate (center), and high (right) fire severity for conifer (top row) and eucalypt (bottom
911 row) forests.
- 912 Fig. 3. Relationships between plot fire severity (mean values by severity class and fire) and RBR indices for dry
913 environmental conditions. Results for RBR_{HV} polarization (left panel) and RBR_{RFDI} (right panel).
- 914 Fig. 4 Error metrics for each fire when estimating fire severity at plot level (left) and for the overstory layer (right) from
915 RBR_{HV}. Shown are: the model coefficient of determination (R^2), the correlation coefficient between predicted and observed
916 values (r), the agreement between observed and predicted fire severity by intervals (Cohen's weighted kappa) and the root
917 mean squared error (RMSE) of the predicted values.
- 918 Fig. 5. Predicted vs. observed fire severity for the three main forest types analyzed (conifers, eucalypt and mixed forests).
919 Values predicted by local empirical regression models using cross-validation with bootstrapping. Plot (left panel) and
920 overstory (right panel) fire severity. For better visibility only 100 randomly selected pairs are displayed. The dashed line
921 represents perfect agreement between observed and predicted values (1:1 line).
- 922 Fig. 6 Relationship between plot fire severity (mean values by severity class and fire) and standardized RBR (z-score) for
923 dry conditions. Left panel presents results for RBR_{HV} while the right panel presents results for RBR_{RFDI}.
- 924 Fig. 7 Standardized RBR_{HV} (z-score) as a function of fire severity. The vertical bars represent the 95% confidence interval.
925 The values were computed using all available field plots for dry dates. The left panel presents values based on fire severity
926 at plot level while the right panel presents values based on overstory fire severity.
- 927 Fig. 8 Comparison of Cohen's kappa obtained using common thresholds vs. species specific thresholds in standardized
928 models (left) and local empirical models vs. common thresholds on standardized RBR indices (right).
- 929 Fig. 9 Maps of overstory fire severity obtained using common thresholds and dry acquisitions (HV polarization). Notice the
930 detection of another fire scar (South Omak Lake fire, 2007.08.30) located northwest from Colombia River Road fire. The
931 area detected as low-medium fire severity southwest of Kinglake fire perimeter is caused by inter-annual radar signal
932 change over cropping areas. Such effects are usually filtered out when several pre- and post-fire images are available.

Fig. 1 Locations of the studied fires showing fire perimeter and the CBI field plots overlaid on pre-fire Landsat images

Conifer forests - Columbia River Road

Eucalypt forest - Kinglake

Fig. 2 Examples of low (left), moderate (center), and high (right) fire severity for conifer (top row) and eucalypt (bottom row) forests.

Fig. 3. Relationships between plot fire severity (mean values by severity class and fire) and RBR indices for dry environmental conditions. Results for RBR_{HV} polarization (left panel) and RBR_{RFDI} (right panel).

Fig. 4 Error metrics for each fire when estimating fire severity at plot level (left) and for the overstory layer (right) from RBR_{HV} . Shown are: the model coefficient of determination (R^2), the correlation coefficient between predicted and observed values (r), the agreement between observed and predicted fire severity by intervals (Cohen's weighted kappa) and the root mean squared error (RMSE) of the predicted values.

Fig. 5. Predicted vs. observed fire severity for the three main forest types analyzed (conifers, eucalypt and mixed forests). Values predicted by local empirical regression models using cross-validation with bootstrapping. Plot (left panel) and overstory (right panel) fire severity. For better visibility only 100 randomly selected pairs are displayed. The dashed line represents perfect agreement between observed and predicted values (1:1 line).

Fig. 6 Relationship between plot fire severity (mean values by severity class and fire) and standardized RBR (z-score) for dry conditions. Left panel presents results for RBR_{HV} while the right panel presents results for RBR_{RFDI} .

Fig. 7 Standardized RBR_{HV} (z-score) as a function of fire severity. The vertical bars represent the 95% confidence interval. The values were computed using all available field plots for dry dates. The left panel presents values based on fire severity at plot level while the right panel presents values based on overstory fire severity.

Fig. 8 Comparison of Cohen's kappa obtained using common thresholds vs. species specific thresholds in standardized models (left) and local empirical models vs. common thresholds on standardized RBR indices (right).

Fig. 9 Maps of overstory fire severity obtained using common thresholds and dry acquisitions (HV polarization). Notice the detection of another fire scar (South Omak Lake fire, 2007.08.30) located northwest from Columbia River Road fire. The area detected as low-medium fire severity southwest of Kinglake fire perimeter is caused by inter-annual radar signal change over cropping areas. Such effects are usually filtered out when several pre- and post-fire images are available.

Table 1 Forest type characteristics. AGB - Above Ground Biomass, DBH - Diameter at Breast Height.

	Mean (Max) biomass (t ha ⁻¹)	Mean DBH (cm)	Mean (Max) height (m)	Forest type	CBI range Plot (Overstory)
Kinglake: wet forest	570 (1244)	40	20 (54)	Eucalypt	
Kinglake: damp forest	382 (456)	30	17 (32)	Eucalypt	
Kinglake: forby forest	280 (587)	35	20 (32)	Eucalypt	
Iron Complex	266 (407)	18-67*	9-33* (64)	Mixed	0-3 (0-3)
Rooster Rock	84 (301)	20-42*	13-27* (67)	Coniferous	
Columbia River Rd.	69 (206)	14-34*	11-20* (46)	Coniferous	
Aliaga, Los Olmos, Zuera	30 (145)	20	8 (20)	Coniferous	

* species dependent

Table 2 Results of local empirical modeling for each fire, SAR metric and environmental conditions (dry vs. wet) when estimating fire severity at plot and overstory level, respectively. Model fit and errors are given by the coefficient of determination (R^2), the correlation coefficient between predicted and observed values (r), the root mean squared error (RMSE) of the predicted values, the bias and, the agreement between observed and predicted fire severity by intervals (Cohen's weighted kappa). SAR metrics were computed as the average backscatter of pre- and post-fire datasets except for Rooster Rock and Kinglake fires under dry conditions for which only one post-fire dataset was available.

Fire	R^2	r	RMSE	bias	kappa
Dry conditions					
RBR _{HV} (CBI plot / CBI overstory)					
Aliaga	0.60/0.80	0.75/0.88	0.72/0.54	0.01/-0.01	0.59/0.85
LosOlmos	0.60/0.70	0.71/0.80	0.62/0.62	0.02/0.00	0.54/0.76
Zuera	0.86/0.78	0.92/0.88	0.37/0.51	0.00/0.00	0.86/0.79
Iron complex	0.28/0.46	0.48/0.65	0.85/0.97	-0.00/0.01	0.25/0.49
Rooster Rock	0.62/0.61	0.76/0.76	0.65/0.77	0.00/0.01	0.60/0.66
Columbia River Road	0.65/0.64	0.78/0.77	0.60/0.78	0.00/0.03	0.69/0.72
Kinglake: Wet forest	0.62/0.66	0.76/0.79	0.52/0.55	0.00/0.00	0.59/0.69
Kinglake: Damp forest	0.42/0.59	0.63/0.76	0.60/0.60	-0.0/0.00	0.50/0.64
Kinglake: Forby forest	0.48/0.62	0.68/0.78	0.67/0.65	0.00/0.00	0.55/0.66
RBR _{HH} (CBI plot / CBI overstory)					
Aliaga	0.52/0.70	0.69/0.83	0.79/0.65	0.02/0.01	0.51/0.77
LosOlmos	0.48/0.55	0.65/0.71	0.67/0.74	0.02/0.01	0.61/0.58
Zuera	0.69/0.64	0.83/0.79	0.57/0.67	0.02/0.01	0.70/0.68
Iron complex	0.15/0.16	0.30/0.31	0.93/1.22	0.00/0.01	0.16/0.17
Rooster Rock	0.26/0.27	0.42/0.44	0.91/1.07	0.00/0.01	0.43/0.36
Columbia River Road	0.41/0.43	0.59/0.62	0.78/0.97	-0.00/0.01	0.37/0.59
Kinglake: Wet forest	0.22/0.43	0.45/0.64	0.76/0.66	0.00/0.00	0.27/0.56
Kinglake: Damp forest	0.32/0.43	0.54/0.64	0.79/0.80	0.00/0.00	0.36/0.52
Kinglake: Forby forest	0.14/0.25	0.34/0.48	0.88/0.89	0.00/0.00	0.17/0.30
RBR _{RFDI} (CBI plot / CBI overstory)					
Aliaga	0.35/0.47	0.56/0.67	0.90/0.87	0.04/0.04	0.47/0.58
LosOlmos	0.32/0.40	0.53/0.64	0.75/0.81	0.04/0.04	0.39/0.47
Zuera	0.57/0.55	0.78/0.76	0.64/0.72	0.05/0.05	0.61/0.57
Iron complex	0.05/0.12	0.09/0.23	0.98/1.25	0.01/0.01	0.09/0.09
Rooster Rock	0.29/0.24	0.47/0.42	0.88/1.08	0.00/0.00	0.25/0.20
Columbia River Road	0.27/0.29	0.45/0.48	0.87/1.09	0.00/0.01	0.40/0.38
Kinglake: Wet forest	0.44/0.38	0.62/0.58	0.64/0.74	-0.0/0.00	0.32/0.49
Kinglake: Damp forest	0.26/0.33	0.50/0.57	0.67/0.76	0.00/0.00	0.39/0.38
Kinglake: Forby forest	0.36/0.39	0.60/0.62	0.74/0.82	0.01/0.01	0.41/0.45
Wet conditions					
RBR _{HH} (CBI plot / CBI overstory)					
Kinglake: Wet forest	0.36/0.42	0.57/0.62	0.72/0.75	-0.00/0.00	0.33/0.45
Kinglake: Damp forest	0.47/0.37	0.68/0.58	0.67/0.80	0.00/-0.00	0.47/0.41
Kinglake: Forby forest	0.44/0.39	0.64/0.60	0.63/0.67	-0.00/0.00	0.45/0.22
RBR _{RFDI} (CBI plot / CBI overstory)					
Kinglake: Wet forest	0.44/0.35	0.63/0.55	0.63/0.72	-0.00/0.00	0.43/0.31
Kinglake: Damp forest	0.28/0.32	0.50/0.55	0.71/0.79	0.00/0.00	0.29/0.35
Kinglake: Forby forest	0.34/0.36	0.57/0.58	0.75/0.82	0.01/0.00	0.34/0.45

Table 3 Cut thresholds for mapping fire severity using the standardized RBR. The thresholds were computed using all available datasets as well as for two main forest types (conifers and eucalypt) at plot and respectively overstory levels. For eucalypt forest thresholds for wet environmental conditions are also provided

SAR metric	CBI layer	Unchanged CBI=0	Low severity 0<CBI<1	Moderate severity 1<CBI<2	Moderate-high severity 2<CBI<2.5	High severity 2.5<CBI<3
Dry conditions – all forests						
RBR _{HV}	Plot	> 0.97	0.97 – 0.40	0.40 – -0.12	-0.12 – -0.91	< -0.91
	Overstory	> 0.88	0.88 – 0.39	0.39 – -0.31	-0.31 – -0.93	< -0.93
RBR _{HH}	Plot	> 0.74	0.74 – 0.14	0.14 – 0.06	0.06 – -0.72	< -0.72
	Overstory	> 0.62	0.62 – 0.54	0.54 – -0.23	-0.23 – -0.87	< -0.87
RBR _{RFDI}	Plot	< -0.60	-0.60 – -0.47	-0.47 – 0.04	0.04 – 0.80	> 0.80
	Overstory	< -0.80	-0.80 – -0.28	-0.28 – 0.16	0.16 – 0.85	> 0.85
Dry conditions - Coniferous						
RBR _{HV}	Plot	> 1.07	1.07 – 0.50	0.50 – -0.15	-0.15 – -0.88	< -0.88
	Overstory	> 0.87	0.87 – 0.38	0.38 – -0.39	-0.39 – -0.92	< -0.92
RBR _{HH}	Plot	> 0.94	0.94 – 0.77	0.77 – -0.12	-0.12 – -0.95	< -0.95
	Overstory	> 0.80	0.80 – 0.51	0.51 – -0.34	-0.34 – -0.98	< -0.98
RBR _{RFDI}	Plot	< -0.72	-0.72 – -0.68	-0.68 – -0.06	-0.06 – 0.74	> 0.74
	Overstory	< -0.79	-0.79 – -0.27	-0.27 – 0.11	0.11 – 0.75	> 0.75
Dry conditions – Eucalyptus forests						
RBR _{HV}	Plot	> 0.93	0.93 – 0.48	0.48 – -0.14	-0.14 – -1.08	< -1.08
	Overstory	> 0.95	0.95 – 0.46	0.46 – -0.30	-0.30 – -0.82	< -0.82
RBR _{HH}	Plot	> 0.55	0.55 – -0.02	-0.02 – 0.22	0.22 – -0.57	< -0.57
	Overstory	> 0.44	0.44 – 0.81	0.81 – -0.22	-0.22 – -0.75	< -0.75
RBR _{RFDI}	Plot	< -0.55	-0.55 – -0.52	-0.52 – 0.31	0.31 – 0.92	> 0.92
	Overstory	< -0.72	-0.72 – -0.37	-0.37 – 0.44	0.44 – 1.04	> 1.04
Wet conditions – Eucalyptus forests						
RBR _{HH}	Plot	< -0.56	-0.56 – -0.30	-0.30 – 0.41	0.41 – 0.78	> 0.78
	Overstory	< -0.80	-0.80 – -0.01	-0.01 – 0.38	0.38 – 0.85	> 0.85
RBR _{RFDI}	Plot	< -0.76	-0.76 – -0.43	-0.43 – 0.47	0.47 – 0.92	> 0.92
	Overstory	< -0.79	-0.79 – -0.03	-0.03 – 0.40	0.40 – 0.93	> 0.93

Table 4 Agreement (Cohen`s weighted kappa) between observed fire severity and fire severity estimated using cut thresholds for plot and overstory layers. Each column contains values derived using common thresholds (left) and forest type specific thresholds (right). Data correspond to images acquired under dry conditions. SAR metrics were computed as the average backscatter of pre- and post-fire datasets except for Rooster Rock and Kinglake fires for which only one post-fire dataset was available

Fire	Severity level:	RBR _{HV}		RBR _{HH}		RBR _{RFDI}	
		Plot	Overstory	Plot	Overstory	Plot	Overstory
Aliaga		0.68/0.65	0.83/0.83	0.59/0.63	0.74/0.70	0.50/0.40	0.59/0.58
LosOlmos		0.69/0.70	0.78/0.78	0.54/0.47	0.60/0.52	0.35/0.46	0.53/0.53
Zuera		0.85/0.82	0.75/0.74	0.70/0.68	0.68/0.68	0.66/0.66	0.65/0.68
Iron complex		0.35/ na	0.33/ na	0.17/ na	0.05/ na	0.01/ na	0.03/ na
Rooster Rock		0.70/0.72	0.59/0.59	0.44/0.46	0.40/0.42	0.31/0.27	0.16/0.19
Columbia River Road		0.62/0.67	0.54/0.54	0.45/0.32	0.42/0.30	0.11/0.12	0.02/0.04
Kinglake		0.49/0.45	0.63/0.62	0.27/ na	0.34/ na	0.21/0.31	0.17/0.27

Appendix A

Table A1

SAR data sets available for each fire and environmental conditions at acquisition. The cumulative precipitation (three days prior to acquisition) is given for the closest meteorological stations. In parenthesis the rainfall (mm) recorded for the SAR acquisition date is provided. Post-fire data sets are shown in italics. The fire date is shown in parenthesis.

Fire name, Fire date and SAR acquisition mode	SAR acquisition date	Cumulative (day) precipitations (mm)			
		9567F	9550D	9567U	9566
Aliaga and Los Olmos (2009.07.21-29) Fine Beam Dual Path 665 Frame 800	2007.06.30				0.2 (0.0)
	2007.08.15				0.6 (0.0)
	2007.09.30				2.2 (0.0)
	2008.05.17				38.0 (0.4)
	2008.07.02				1.8 (0.0)
	<i>2009.08.20</i>	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)
	<i>2009.10.05</i>	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)
	<i>2010.05.23</i> <i>2010.07.08</i>				0.0 (0.0) 1.4 (1.4)
Zuera (2008.08.06-16) Fine Beam Dual Path 665 Frame 830	2007.06.30	9496	9495U	9434	
	2007.08.15	0.0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	
	2007.09.30	0.0 (0.0)	2.1 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	
	2008.05.17		0.8 (0.0)	2.4 (0.0)	
	2008.07.02	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	15.9 (0.0)	
	<i>2009.08.20</i>	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	
	<i>2009.10.05</i>	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	
	<i>2010.05.23</i> <i>2010.07.08</i>			0.0 (0.0) 0.0 (0.0)	
Iron Complex (2008.06.21) Fine Beam Dual Path 223 Frame 800	2007.06.14	USC00040738	USC00049490	US1CATY0003	US1CATY0010
	2007.09.14	0.0 (0.0)	N/A	N/A	N/A
	2008.05.01	0.0 (0.0)	N/A	N/A	N/A
	2008.06.16	0.8 (0.0)	0.3 (0.0)	N/A	N/A
	2008.08.01 ^{nu}	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	N/A	N/A
	<i>2009.06.19</i>	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)
	<i>2010.05.07</i>	0.0 (0.0)	0.3 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)
Rooster Rock (2010.08.02) Fine Beam Dual Path 218 Frame 870	2007.06.21	USS0021E07S	USS0021E07S		
	2007.08.06	5.0 (N/A)	N/A		
	2008.06.23	7.6 (N/A)	2.3 (0.0)		
	2009.06.26	0.0 (N/A)	2.5 (0.0)		
	2010.06.29	2.5 (2.5)	0.0 (N/A)		
	<i>2010.09.29</i>	N/A	N/A		
	0.0 (N/A)	2.5 (0.0)			
Columbia River Road (2008.08.07) Fine Beam Dual Path 214 Frame 950	2007.06.11	USC00451400	USC00451767	USS0019A13S	
	2007.07.27	0.0 (0.0)	0.5 (0.0)	N/A	
	2008.07.29	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	N/A	
	2008.07.29	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	N/A	
	2008.09.13	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	2.5 (N/A)	
	2009.08.01	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	12.7 (12.7)	
	2010.08.04	12 (1.8)	0.0 (0.0)	10.4 (0.0)	
	2010.09.19	19.0 (11.2)	18.5 (11.2)	10.4 (7.6)	
<i>2010.11.04</i>	2.0 (0.0) ^{ft}	2.8 (0.0) ^{ft}	12.9 (5.1) ^{sn}		

Table A1 (continuing)

Fire name, Fire date and SAR acquisition mode	SAR acquisition date	Cumulative precipitations (mm)			
		088060	086142	086009	086366
Kingleake East (2009.02.07-03.14) Fine Beam Dual Path 381 Frame 6420	2007.07.02	4.4 (0.8)	N/A	31.9 (12.0)	49.4 (6.9)
	2007.08.17	2.0 (0.0)	N/A	19.3 (4.8)	16.7 (0.0)
	2007.10.02	10.8 (0.0)	N/A	8.0 (0.0)	20 (0.0)
	2008.05.19	25.6 (1.0)	42.4 (14.1)	30.3 (10)	26 (8.5)
	2008.07.04	25.6 (3.4)	7.8 (2.0)	38.4 (9.6)	27.4 (6.9)
	2008.08.19	23.6 (2.2)	30.3 (2.1)	22.4 (5.6)	24.3 (6.1)
	2008.10.04	9.4 (9.4)	10 (10)	8.5 (8.5)	14.0 (7)
	2009.07.07	14.6 (2.8)	31.0 (0.0)	36.4 (9.1)	8.9 (2.4)
	2009.08.22	7.8 (0.0)	11.2 (2.8)	18.6 (1.5)	18.0 (5.4)
	2009.10.07	27.6 (19.4)	23.0 (6.8)	9.4 (3.1)	5.7 (1.4)
	2010.05.25	12.6 (12.2)	6.0 (6.0)	7.0 (1.7)	5.8 (1.5)
2010.08.25	17.6 (15.4)	21.8 (15.8)	28.9 (7.2)	22.3 (5.6)	
Kingleake West (2009.02.07-03.14) Fine Beam Dual Path 382 Frame 6420	2007.07.19	27.0 (10.8)	N/A	41.3 (10.3)	38.7 (9.7)
	2007.09.03	1.6 (0.2)	N/A	7.9 (2.6)	8.0 (2.7)
	2007.10.19	1.0 (0.0)	N/A	5.7 (0.0)	4.0 (0.0)
	2008.09.05	2.2 (0.2)	3.8 (0.0)	12.3 (3.1)	9.9 (2.5)
	2008.10.21	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	1.0 (1.0)	0.0 (0.0)
	2009.03.08nu	12.0 (0.0)	22.6 (0.0)	N/A	16.5 (4.1)
	2009.07.24	12.0 (0.4)	19. (0.0)	8.6 (2.2)	21.5 (5.4)
	2009.09.08	15 (8.8)	39.9 (34.8)	5.3 (1.3)	9.2 (2.3)
	2009.10.24dd	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0.0)	3.4 (0.5)
	2010.09.11	14.8 (5.4)	9.0 (4.5)	44.3 (11.1)	44.0 (3.3)
2010.10.27	13.6 (2.6)	9.4 (0.0)	20.7 (5.2)	19.7 (4.9)	
Kingleake East (2009.02.07-03.14) Fine Beam Single Path 381 Frame 6420	2006.12.30	4.2(0)	N/A	32.2(0)	2.4(0)
	2007.02.14	2.0(1.4)	N/A	0(0)	3.4(0)
	2008.01.02	0 (0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
	2008.02.17	0(0)	10.8(1.7)	5.5(2.5)	0.6(0)
	2009.01.04	0(0)	8(0)	0.8(0.2)	9.0(0)
	2009.02.19nu	0(0)	0(0)	N/A	0(0)
	2010.01.07dd	0(0)	0.2(0)	20.3(5.1)	0(0)
	2010.02.22	7.4(7.4)	10.8(10.8)	5.1(1.5)	2.3(2.3)
	2011.01.10	11.4(0.8)	24.6(12.3)	24.2(24.2)	2.6(1)
	2011.02.25	0(0)	7.85(0)	11.1(0)	1.2(0)

dd - dry date post-fire image used in the analysis, nu - not used in the analysis (acquired during fire), ft - freezing temperatures, sn - snow fall

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